

PLANNING CURRICULUM AND SYLLABUS

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Abstract. Curriculum development is a purposeful, progressive, and systematic process to create positive improvements in the educational system. The development process systematically organizes what will be taught, who will be teaching, and how content is taught. Analyzing a visual representation of the curriculum is a quick and easy way to identify potential gaps or alignment issues. A syllabus reflects the instructor's feelings, attitudes, and beliefs about the subject matter, teaching, learning, and students. It should outline what is expected to happen during the semester, delineate the responsibilities of students and of the instructor.

A successful formal coaching and gaining knowledge of system calls for right choice and association of the teaching material. The selection and sequencing of learning content and methodologies take place in the curriculum, syllabus, scheme of work and lesson plan stages. We argue that the difference among them is not usually clear to a significant number of teachers.

Curriculum development is a purposeful, progressive, and systematic process to create positive improvements in the educational system. All curriculum designs endeavour to address four curriculum components: why do we initiate instruction? What should we teach? How can we interconnect target learning experiences? What have we realized and what actions should we take accordingly in relation to the instructional program, learners, and teachers.

There are 3 fundamental styles of curriculum layout - subject-centered, learner-centered and problem-centered. Subject-centered curriculum design describes what needs to be studied and how it should be studied. Designing a curriculum for middle school students with both elementary and high school curricula in mind helps to make sure that learning goals are aligned [1].

Learner-targeted curriculum layout is supposed to empower freshmen and permit them to form their schooling via choices. Developing differentiated practise places strain at the trainer to create practice and/or discover substances which are conducive to every scholar's gaining knowledge of desires. It additionally calls for that instructors stability scholar wishes and hobbies with scholar desires and required outcomes, which isn't an smooth stability to obtain. Problem-targeted curricula cognizance on coaching college students the way to

study a trouble and give you a solution. Students are uncovered to actual-existence troubles, which facilitates them increase abilities which are transferable to the actual world. Problem-targeted curriculum layout will increase the relevance of the curriculum and lets in college students to be innovative and innovate as they're gaining knowledge of [2].

The version suggests a round system in which volunteer education offers remarks for brand new substances or revisions to the present curriculum. The group makes systematic selections approximately the goal audience, supposed out-comes (targets), content material, strategies, and assessment strategies. Draft curriculum merchandise are developed, tested, evaluated, and redesigned - if necessary.

The curriculum design suggestions provided below might assist instructors in managing each stage of the curriculum design process.

- Early in the curriculum design process, identify the needs of stakeholders (i.e., students). This may be accomplished through needs analysis, which entails the gathering and analysis of learner-related data. This information might include what learners currently know as well as what they need to know to be proficient in a specific area or skill. It might also include data on student perspectives, strengths, and weaknesses.
- Make a list of learning objectives and results. This will allow you to focus on the curriculum's intended purpose and plan instruction that will achieve the

desired results.

- Determine the limits that will affect your curriculum design. Time, for example, is a typical restriction that must be taken into account. The period has a limited number of hours, days, weeks, or months. If there isn't enough time to give all of the intended teaching, learning results will suffer.
- Consider developing a curriculum map to appropriately assess the chronology and coherence of instruction.
- Curriculum mapping creates visual diagrams or curriculum indexes. Analyzing a visual representation of the curriculum is a quick and easy way to identify potential gaps, redundancies, or alignment issues in instruction sequencing. Curriculum maps can be created on paper, as well as with software or online services designed specifically for this purpose.
- Determine the instructional methods that will be used throughout the course and consider how they will interact with the various learning styles of the students. If the instructional methods are incompatible with the curriculum, the instructional design or curriculum design must be revised.

A syllabus contains the aims and assessment objectives of a subject at a particular level of education. It also contains the sequence of the content knowledge to be taught, and the assessment procedures to be adopted. According to Taruvinga and Moyo [3], this school syllabus serves as the point of reference for the schemes of work.

The quality of a syllabus is a fairly reliable indicator of the quality of teaching and learning that will take place in a course. It behooves instructors to make the effort to construct a high-quality syllabus. A syllabus reflects the instructor's feelings, attitudes, and beliefs about the subject matter, teaching, learning, and students.

A syllabus should make the rules for the course clear. It should outline what is expected to happen during the semester, delineate the responsibilities of students and of the instructor, and describe appropriate procedures and course policies. The curriculum development process systematically organizes what will be taught, who will be teaching, and how content is taught.

The following diagram illustrates the four stages of the curriculum development process: I) Planning, II) Content and Methods, III) Implementation, and IV) Evaluation and Reporting [4]. It is important to acknowledge that things do not always work exactly as depicted in a model! These steps are not always separate and distinct, but may overlap and occur concurrently.

The most important task is to keep the learner in mind and involve them in process. Because a curriculum map is essentially a plan for learning [5], it requires to approach professionally to be fulfilled successfully.

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